

TECHNOLOGY FOCUSED ON THE SUSTAINABLE USE OF URBAN WASTE WITH THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW RECYCLED PRODUCTS

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Abstract : This project demonstrates the large percentage of garbage generated daily in Brazil, representing inconsistencies and weaknesses in solid waste management. The objective is to produce a bioplastic and to evaluate its biodegradability using sources of organic and polymeric origin. The first time to synthesize the organic material using a potato conditioned inside the cells of the landfill but later use other organic sources, in addition to plastic materials based on polystyrene. The project is justified, with the use of innovation in recycling processes to promote the restoration of ecological balance in certain environments that have been affected by pollution. The method used in the study is based on the methodology of "casting" based on bibliographic research in scientific articles. Considering that all plants can be hosts of one or more endophytic fungi, and these have great biotechnological potential the work will study the feasibility of using endophytic fungi to renew the concept of recycling. This project is multidisciplinary and seeks to dialogue with other areas, such as biology, and chemistry beyond engineering. Therefore, it is concluded the concern with the environment, the conscience environment, and the reduction of environmental impacts in the face of the extreme need to adopt sustainable recycling activities, aiming to guarantee a future for the next generations.

Keywords : Solid Waste. Biodegradability. Endophytic Fungi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the total annual generation of solid waste worldwide is approximately 17 billion tons and is expected to reach 27 billion by 2050 (Karak et al., 2012).

Solid waste management is known to be a major contributor to many different environmental problems such as ecosystem damage and resource depletion due to inefficient recycling systems (Lazarevic et al., 2010).

The National Solid Waste Policy (Law 12.305/2010) is extremely important in this process, in which the principles, objectives and instruments, focus on integrated management in the management of solid waste, the responsibilities of generators, public authorities and applicable economic instruments .

The research project is based on innovation and recycling technology in the search for a technological solution for the production of a biodegradable material and to reduce the degradation time using organic material and polymeric bases in landfill soil or dumps.

The prevalence of landfills demonstrates that a large percentage of the garbage generated daily does not receive adequate treatment, representing inconsistencies and weaknesses in the public management of solid waste in Brazil.

The accumulation of garbage is a phenomenon exclusive to human societies. In a natural system there is no garbage: what is no longer useful for a living being is absorbed by others, in a continuous way. However, our way of life produces a very large amount and variety of garbage on a daily basis, causing the pollution of soil, water and air with toxic waste, in addition to promoting the proliferation of disease vectors. (HESS, 2002).

Despite the many benefits that plastic brings to society, its waste is harmful. The large volume of plastic materials, the huge amount of post-consumer disposal and the environmental impacts caused by incorrect disposal of waste, which is not biodegradable, contribute to polymeric pollution (ANA, 2019).

The plastics industry is in constant development, with the emergence of technologies to meet new demands that arise every day, and it is not surprising that world plastic production reached 265 million tons in 2010 (UNESA, 2019).

In addition, plastics can harm the health of humans and animals, mainly because of the chemical additives used in their manufacture. Regulatory instruments aimed at mitigating the effects of plastics on human and environmental health need to follow its cycle, from production, use and disposal.

In the midst of all the negative impacts on the environment related to the use of plastics, the search for technologies that replace these materials is increasing. In this scenario, bioplastics stand out as a sustainable and satisfactory alternative, since they have properties and applications that are generally similar to those of plastics derived from oil, gas or coal.

Despite the challenges related to bioplastics, such as the higher cost of the raw material, the lack of incentive policies for the development of more sustainable products and the consolidation of the industrial process focused on conventional plastics, their production has grown. Data show that between 2018 and 2019, the expansion of installed capacity was 5%, reaching 2.1 million tons (ANA, 2019).

The main raw material for the manufacture of plastics is oil, but only 4% of the world's oil and gas production is used as a raw material for the production of plastics, and another 3 to 4% is used as energy in the process (HOPEWELL, DVORAKE KOSIOR, 2009, THOMPSON et al., 2009).

Recycling is traditionally defined as the process of reusing waste, in which its components are separated, transformed and recovered, involving savings in raw materials and energy, combating waste, reducing environmental pollution and valuing waste, with change of conception in relation to them (PNUD, 1998).

The combination of waste, plastic and organic, creates a life cycle for new products in this innovative recycling model, which reverse logistics seeks to generate a hybrid polymer, which can be used to mold new sustainable and ecologically correct products, since now, the degradation time becomes naturally supported by Nature.

The problem presents the large amount of garbage accumulated and discarded improperly. Is the organic-polymeric recycling solution outside of conventional standards a new alternative in the recycling process?

The general objective is to be able to aggregate organic waste, preferably those rich in fibers, in order to reuse polymeric waste in order to synthesize them in a single process with the creation of a plastic with organic content and with this increases the degradation. Specifically serve the local community with a proposal for the 5R application (Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Recycle and Transform); suggest to local bodies a sustainable creation of biomaterials, with the aim of producing biodegradable products.

The relevance of this project is to carry out an improvement study through innovative techniques and forms of continued exploration on the ideal conditions for the use of recycling using technological innovation in the transformation processes.

The vast majority of polymers are formed by hydrocarbons, in such a way that this ensures longevity and other properties that keep them stable for a long time (ROSA et al, 2002). In contrast, plastic produced with organic aggregates is more vulnerable to degradation. The organic waste will usually be used dispersed in a polymeric matrix producing biodegradable plastic.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 History of polymers

In the history of humanity there are several discoveries that changed the course of its development. One of them occurred with the appearance of the polymer, which was created accidentally, was occupying its space, developing and facilitating people's lives, due to its wide use (SANTOS, 2010).

In general; polymers, are formed by the grouping of several monomers, through the polymerization reaction. In this process, depending on the conditions under which the reaction occurs, a polymer with 2,000 to 100,000 monomers can be formed. Thus, the molecular masses of polymers can vary from 56,000 to 2,800,000 units (FELTRE, 2004).

Polymers are macromolecules formed by repeating units (monomers) that interact with each other, predominantly by covalent bonds, which give materials attributes such as electrical insulation. Plastics, in turn, are materials that have as raw material a synthetic polymerized organic substance, which presents high malleability, easily transformable through the use of heat and pressure, and can be used for the manufacture of various objects. (CASTILLO, 2011).

2.2 Recycling

Recycling is one of the most advantageous solid waste treatment alternatives, both from an environmental and social point of view. It reduces the consumption of natural resources, saves energy and water and even reduces the volume of waste and pollution.

In order to attract more investments to the sector, it is necessary to unite efforts between the government, the private sector and society in order to develop adequate policies and overcome prejudices regarding the economic aspects and the reliability of recycled products.

According to the United Nations (USEPA, 2017), recycling is defined as any reprocessing of waste material from a production process and which is diverted from the waste path, except the reuse of fuel.

For the European Environment Agency, recycling is:

A method of resource recovery, involving the collection and treatment of waste from a product, for use as a raw material in the manufacture of the same or a similar product. (2) The European Union waste strategy distinguishes between: (a) reuse of materials without any structural changes to the material; (b) recycling understood as a recycling of materials only, and with a reference to the structural changes of products; and (c) recovery as an energy recovery (EEA, 2014).

The National Solid Waste Policy (BRASIL, 2010) in its third article, item XIV, defines recycling as:

The process of transforming solid waste that involves altering its physical, physical-chemical or biological properties, with a view to transforming it into inputs or new products, observing the conditions and standards established by Organs competent bodies of SISNAMA, if applicable, of SNVS and from SUASA (BRASIL, 2010). Thus, recycling can be a viable alternative to reduce the problems caused by the amounts of solid urban waste generated daily in the world and reduce health and environmental problems and the loss of financial and natural resources resulting from the management of solid urban waste, including provisions inadequate. However, despite all the advantages mentioned, recycling rates are still negligible in many municipalities in developing countries.

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2.3 Endophytic fungi and the production of bioplastics

The material that makes up the inorganic waste does not have a biological origin, it is produced by non-natural means, that is, produced by man, such as plastic. The big problem with this type of waste is its long decomposition time in nature. In the case of organic waste, Brazil produces almost 37 million tons. It's like throwing garbage money in the trash. However, only 1% of what is discarded is reused (ANA, 2019).

A polymer used, very efficient in the production of bioplastics, is the starch found in tubers, cereals and roots. This can be easily transformed into thermoplastic material, offering an important alternative for replacing synthetic polymers in applications where biodegradability is desirable. (RÓZ, 2004).

In the production of bioplastic, endophytic fungi are used, which are a diverse group of ascomycetes defined by their asymptomatic occurrence in plant tissues. Fungi, along with

bacteria and other microorganisms, are excellent models for studies on bioremediation, as they produce a large number of enzymes capable of decomposing almost everything around them. These species of fungi produce an enzyme (*Aspergillus Parasiticus*), capable of degrading the polymeric material, until then considered non-degradable.

The term endophyte, originally described by De Bary in 1866, refers to any microorganism that lives in plant tissues, as distinguished from epiphytes that live on the surface. Different definitions of endophyte are found in the literature, but the widely accepted and used one defined by Bacon and Write is that endophytes are microorganisms that colonize the internal tissues of plants without cause.

They occur throughout the Earth's territory, in natural and anthropogenic communities, colonizing plants in the Arctic, Antarctica, geothermal soils, deserts, oceans, tropical forests, mangroves and coastal forests. In almost all vascular plants, seaweeds, mosses and ferns studied so far, endophytic bacteria and fungi have been found.

Figure 1- Isolation and purification of endophytic fungi

Source : Silva (2010)

3 METHOD

The methodology used to prepare this project presents a case study based on an environmental project based on real problems, which can be confused with project-based teaching or *Problem-based Learning* (PBL). The eligibility criteria were designed to capture

environmental attitudes of recycling solid waste; building green consumption; as well as reverse and multidisciplinary logistics analysis.

3.1 Research location

The research was carried out by monitoring the development of this project at a University of Rio de Janeiro, in a landfill in the Lagos Region.

3.2 Research flow

THEME - PROBLEM - BACKGROUND - OBJECTIVES - THEORETICAL FOUNDATION - METHODOLOGY - CASE STUDY - RESULT AND DISCUSSION - FINAL CONSIDERATIONS - BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES

3.3 Search classification

The base of the research presents its classification as to the nature of an applied research with a qualitative approach, as to the objective of an exploratory research project and in relation to its procedure, technique and a documentary survey.

4 CASE STUDY

The research project is based on recycling technology in the search for a technological solution for the production of a biodegradable plastic and to evaluate its biodegradability using, at first, a membrane synthesized from potato starch, to make a comparison with the biodegradability in synthesized membranes with organic and polymeric material. The urban solid waste disposal area is located in the municipalities of the Lagos Region (currently, for this project, they include São Pedro da Aldeia, Cabo Frio, Arraial do Cabo, Búzios, Casimiro de Abreu, Silva Jardim, Araruama and Iguaba Grande).

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The production of the bioplastic is based on the methodology (casting), which consists of solubilization in a solvent (DMO), as well as application on a support for solvent evaporation and consequent formation of a continuous matrix that gives rise to the film. In the synthesis of the biodegradable film on the bench, initially the organic material was obtained through a mechanical process of grinding potatoes; plus the association of polystyrene in the separation process in a waste collection.

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is a promising tuber in the starch polymer industry. However, despite being prominent in the food sector, of the total potato produced, approximately 35% (peel and rest of pulp) is discarded in the industrialization process. It is speculated that in Brazil more than 300 thousand tons of potato skins are discarded per year, concentrating around 25.60% of the total potato starch. Thus, the use of potato skins for the production of bioplastics becomes feasible (BALSALOBRE, 1995).

Figure 2 – Potato source

Source : Author (2019)

5.1 Beginning of activities

In this phase, a bibliographical study was carried out, in order to assist in the methodology to be applied throughout the study.

5.2 Sample collection

To collect the samples, potatoes taken from the landfill were used, which were exposed to that environment, in order to compare the results in use when they are exposed to biological agents capable of modifying or decomposing pollutants.

5.3 Weighing of samples

At this stage in the laboratory, the potato underwent physical and chemical processes, and the weights of the masses of the polymers to which they were associated, PS (Polystyrene) and the potato mass to be used in the synthesis of the bioplastic were recorded.

LINGUAGENS E SUAS TECNOLOGIAS
Romantismo 3^o Geração - O Navio Negreiro / Castro Alves

Vânia Soares de Souza¹

O Navio Negreiro é uma obra do escritor baiano romântico Castro Alves (1847-1871) que foi publicada em 1869. Trata-se de uma poesia abolicionista, onde o autor aborda o tema da escravidão no Brasil.

Já na terceira fase, a liberdade e a justiça foram os principais motes, tendo o abolicionismo como marca da produção literária do momento

5.4 Synthesis of samples

At this stage, the samples were synthesized in an Erlimey flask, with DMO (Dichloromethane) solvent solution:

- Polymer, PS and the MB Compatibilizing Agent, and in the center the DMO solvent
- Solubilization of Polymers under Magnetic Stirring
- Agitation of the polymers after pouring into a beaker containing Mashed Potatoes

5.5 Filtering and washing

The mixture of polymer masses and potato organic compound was filtered and washed with distilled water in order to extract excess solvent, before starting the drying process and obtaining the bioplastic film.

Figure 3- Filtering, washing and obtaining a hybrid polymeric mass

Source : Author (2019)

5.6 Scientific and socio-environmental solution

The procedure performed resulted in a film and a bioplastic mass, with a very significant resistance with homogeneous characteristics, that is, with a biodegradable profile, with a shorter degradation time.

Figure 4 - Bioplastic film

Source : Author (2019)

Figure 5 - Hybrid mass

Source : Author (2019)

The treatment of this urban waste increases socio-environmental gains, when opportunities are used in the manufacture of bags and molding of new products with a life cycle in a sustainable way.

5.6.1 Advantages

- Prediction of reduction of 50% to 60% of waste generated in 5 years
- Transformation Recycling
- Employability
- Labor qualification
- Industrial Attractive

6 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Man's perception of nature over time, under different aspects, has not always been compatible with the need to maintain a balanced environment.

Concern for the environment gave rise to environmental awareness, which led to more concerned and demanding consumers regarding socio-environmental issues, mainly related to the environmental impacts generated by industrial processes or by any undertaking.

In view of the preliminary results obtained and their characteristics, based on the methodologies used, it is inferred that it is possible to obtain biodegradable plastic films from starch extracted from potatoes or other organic residues.

Because plastic has starch as its raw material, present in potatoes, it saves the non-renewable resource (fossil) which is the raw material widely used. With such an alternative, the process of obtaining this plastic became more sustainable, since the proposed material is easily obtained.

The project presents solidary and environmental economic relationships, with the purpose of supporting the incubation of enterprises that, by economically disposing of local environmental assets or working for their preservation, use or can develop sustainable economic practices, applying socio-environmental technologies in this process.

This project has a multidisciplinary nature and seeks to dialogue with other areas, such as biology, chemistry in addition to engineering. The relevance of this project was to carry out studies to improve recycling through innovative techniques and forms of continued exploration of the ideal conditions for the use of urban waste, in addition to making recycling more effective with the transformation of new sustainable and ecologically correct products.

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